

FM radio morning programs influence on perception of sexual immorality

Introduction

Morality remains a key pillar in Christian worship. This article is as a result of a research exploring the concept of sexual immorality among Christian teenagers in Nairobi County in Kenya. The researcher conducted four focus group discussions (FGDs) with 32 teenage members of different churches. The focus group discussions had 7, 6, 8 and 11 respondents respectively. All teenage respondents admitted that they listen to morning FM programs on both Kiss 100 FM and Classic 105 FM, popular radio stations in Nairobi. As an introduction to the discussions, the researcher played several randomly selected audio clips from the said stations, to set the pace for discussion. The situation in Nairobi is such that some FM radio stations have adopted catchy topics for discussion in their morning programs. Most of these topics dwell on matters of sexuality and marital issues. These are topics that would not normally be discussed in public in Nairobi, let alone subjected to open broadcast.

Results and discussion

Silverstone (2007, 7) fronts the idea that media can determine what its audience perceive to be right or wrong. He reckons, "... the media provide, with greater or less degrees of consistency, the frameworks (or frame worlds) for the appearance of the other ... and at the same time invite ... a moral response from us, the audience..." This portrays the media as usurping a religious role of setting benchmarks for ethics in the society. As a result, media would determine what their audience term as moral or immoral. Shorter and Njiru (2001, 73) recognize this tendency as an attempt to destroy societal moral fabric.

The study observed that teenagers who were faithful listeners of morning programs on Classic 105 FM and Kiss 100 FM reported ignorance or aloofness on acceptable Christian morality such as truthfulness and sexual purity. In fact, they showed lack of awareness and interest in the subject. A respondent reported, "We are free to make decisions as adults. If I am happy with what I choose to do, no one should judge me" (FGD #1). Such an attitude could readily be attributed to the light manner in which morality was presented in FM radio morning programs. This seemed to militate against the communal nature of life as advocated by Mbiti (1969). In a way, such teenagers appear oblivious to the fact that their decisions directly affected people around them to a very large extent. Another respondent remarked, "Parents need to give us space to live our lives, if one makes mistakes, they learn from it" (FGD#3). A situation like this points at the challenges of parenting in moments of transition. A parent finds himself/herself in a dilemma on whether to stamp one's authority and risk tension at home, or ignore the matter and suffer in silent submission.

According to Mbiti (1969, 213), "There are customs, laws regulations and taboos that govern conduct in society. Any breach of the right conduct amounts to moral evil." Therefore, each person is expected to be of good character, knowing that one's conduct has a direct bearing on the harmony and wellbeing of the entire community. Consequently, in African traditional set up, each person had a corporate duty to ensure that the community was not sinned against through bad deeds. This concept is completely ignored in morning programs aired by both Classic 105 FM and Kiss 100 FM where emphasis is laid on individual contentment above corporate duty.

In order for society to maintain harmony, parents have a duty to bring up their teenagers as upright members of the society (Kisembo, Magesa and Shorter, 1998, 153). These teenagers would in turn transmit positive values to the next generation. In the FGDs, respondents seemed to agree that in the current era, teenagers do not need adult guidance on morality. A respondent remarked, "Sex is normal and everyone is doing it, calling it sinful is wrong" (FGD #2). This was a general feeling,

albeit with different wording. Respondents confirmed that audio clips they had listened to actually mirrored what they knew was taking place in the society. Therefore, they perceived such behavior to be acceptable irrespective of the moral judgment Christianity places on it.

Conclusion

According to this research, the aspect of propagating positive values for posterity appears threatened. Teenagers do not feel obliged to ensure that once they become parents, their own children would guard and respect Christian values. Instead, majority of respondents from FGDs felt that morning programs offered useful advice on parenting. They felt that it was right for the programs to debate programs on sexuality in order to lessen the guilt feeling sexually active teenagers are subjected to. In addition, they said, such a debate that followed would give useful ways to avoid parenting problems. In a sense, this is an indictment on parents showing that teenagers did not appreciate parenting as currently constituted. It was apparent that morning programs on some FM radio stations had helped “normalize” what would otherwise be termed as way-ward behavior in Christian doctrine.

References

- Kisembo, B. Magesa, L. and Shorter A. (1998). *African Christian Marriage*. Nairobi: Pauline Publications.
- Mbiti, J. S. (1969). *African Religions and Philosophy*. Nairobi: Heinemann.
- Shorter, A. and Njiru, J. N. (2001) *New Religious Movements in Africa*. Nairobi: Paulines
- Silverstone, R. (2007). *Media and Morality on the Rise of the Mediapolis*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Audio clips

1. What would be worse, catching partner cheating or getting caught? (TMK, November 5, 2015)
2. My husband can sleep with the boss for a pay hike, wife says (Classic Breakfast, March 4, 2015)
3. Is it right for parents to introduce contraceptives to teenagers? (TMK, May 15, 2015)
4. Man juggles 17 women without their knowledge (Classic Breakfast, April 10, 2015).
5. Why married men cheat with their house helps (Classic Breakfast, March 24, 2015).
6. Every married woman has an exit plan (Classic Breakfast, April 16, 2015).
7. Ladies, would you reveal your actual body count? (Classic Breakfast, July 1, 2015)
8. Exposing your parent’s infidelity (Classic Breakfast, February 26, 2015)